

METHODOLOGY OF USING ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES FOR DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT WORK COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The given article presents the importance of increasing the competence and preparing independent work of future primary school teachers in the conditions of electronic education, methods of increasing competence and preparing independent work, a comparative analysis of the methodological competence of independent work, the content of improving the components of the mechanism for developing the independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *e-learning, primary school subjects, future primary school teacher, independent work competence, methodological competence, e-learning resources.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that the modern development of the nation, fundamental changes in the life and educational activities of the nation have created a need and a number of innovative changes in relation to knowledge about independent work and the worldview of independent work. In this regard, the labor market has a need for a competitive teacher, a person with a set of intellectual, communication, information and other competencies. This in turn led to the introduction of the modern term "teacher" into education.

The use of interactive educational resources in the e-learning environment and ensuring the activity of students in organizing and increasing the efficiency of the educational process on a scientific basis, organizing a joint educational process for students with low and high academic performance, creative and systematic thinking, and independent solutions. -formation of intellectual abilities is one of the expressive tasks.

A modern future primary school teacher must be advanced in all aspects, have deep knowledge of his subject, have teaching skills, love children, know the problem in practice and find ways to solve the problem, as well as know modern methods of independent learning in order to paralyze his methodological reserve.

Definitely, analyzing the requirements for a modern future primary school teacher, we considered it permissible to cite the point of view of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who emphasized that "it is necessary to form and educate patriotic individuals who are able to think independently, who know how to think correctly and perform acceptable work" [1]. Moreover, e-learning will play an important role in preparing such an advanced future primary school teacher. One of the urgent tasks of today is to develop the competence of independent work of a future primary school teacher in the conditions of electronic education, and to improve his methodological training.

At present time it is necessary to take into account a number of scientific and theoretical factors when preparing a teacher who meets the requirements of the modern developed labor market. The main stage in the process of this activity is the competence of the future primary school teacher as the content of a creative approach.

Literature review. Khutorskoy A.V. “uses the concepts of “competence” and “competence” as synonyms for each other and shows the difference between them. Competence is interpreted as a general complex of knowledge acquired by a teacher in terms of interrelated characteristics (knowledge, skills, methods of activity) defined for certain specific topics and processes necessary to obtain quality results in relation to them [4].

The competencies of independent work directly include special or independent labor competence, autocompetence, extreme independent labor competence, and potential competence [6].

In improving independent labor and methodological competence, the motivational, intellectual and creative, self-improvement, social and communicative, effective-final stage is important [5].

It is the initial stage of emphasizing the effectiveness of independent work competencies, the ability to systematically organize the adaptive stage, reflective and active stages, that serves to develop the independent work competence of future teachers [7].

D. O. Khimmatalliev ensures the harmony of independent labor and methodological competence and competence, shows the stages of development of a person’s independent work, the content of competencies, and the personal qualities of specialties in the context of courses [8]. Readiness is considered as a holistic formation of the individual, including motivational, emotional-volitional, attitude-behavioral and evaluative components [9].

Modeling of the pedagogical process is usually based on the construction of thinking, which in a certain sense is similar to the object of research and at the same time, to one degree or another, differs from it. It is known that the word “process” has many meanings. We understand the process as a set of sequential actions to achieve a certain result and form the information culture of a computer science teacher.

O.D. Rakhimov [13], D.S. Tokhtasinova [14] and others conducted research on the problems of creating electronic information educational resources based on web technologies, their implementation and creation of models. The model “Creation of interactive educational resources in an electronic educational environment” proposed in our research work is aimed at training a modern computer science teacher in the conditions of information technology (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Model for creating interactive e-learning resources.

The formation of independent work competence as a result of training a future primary school teacher in the conditions of electronic education can only be carried out under strict adherence to didactic conditions, which are as follows:

a) development and introduction into the educational process of an interdisciplinary course that provides pedagogical support and the provision of organizational and methodological support in the process of forming a modern idea of the competence of future primary school teachers for independent work, their readiness and ability for amateur teaching - awareness;

b) ensure the integrative nature of the process of developing the competence of independent work of future primary school teachers.

I.A. Zimnyaya[10], V.D.Shadrikov[11], Yu.M.Asadov[3], theoretically and methodically analyzing the concept of competence, showed that modern competence can be formed by making the educational program prepared for future teacher.

Analysis and results. In our opinion, the development of independent work competence is called:

self-reflection and understanding of the necessary concepts after acquiring the competence to work independently in an e-learning environment;

achieving goals through an e-learning environment;

practice self-improvement and self-correction using e-learning materials.

In our opinion, the formation of independent work competence is carried out in several stages: knowledge about independent work→independent work activity→experience of independent work.

These days the future primary school teacher must gain a place in the labor market through knowledge of independent work→independent work activity→experience of independent work and must develop a number of skills and competencies of independent work. Based on the existing skills of the future primary school teacher, it is necessary to determine the directions for acquiring the level of existing personal and independent competencies:

1. The knowledge acquired by the teacher is reflected in the following processes of independent work:

a) the amount of information available and used from the environment and its complexity;

b) novelty and novelty of the knowledge acquired;

c) the ratio of existing theoretical and practical knowledge to each other.

2. The teacher's skills and practical skills are presented:

a) the variety of possibilities for fully performing independent work, the need to be able to choose opportunities to complete assigned tasks, develop its main paths and directions;

3) Available competencies include the following components:

a) the ability to work independently;

b) field of activity [2].

Based on the above objectives, we believe that the components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers have the following compatibility:

Combination of components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence (Table 1)

Competence in independent work	Methodological competence	Independent labor and methodological competence
Uniqueness	Activity design	Modernization of the educational process
Thirst for theoretical and practical knowledge.	Mastering theoretical and practical knowledge of the lesson.	Practical testing of acquired theoretical knowledge at the stages of self-study and master classes.
Practical skill	Following the stages of the lesson,	Taking into account the dynamics of learning in the educational process before organizing activities (in particular, identifying problems and gaps), applying innovations of technological development in subjects taught in primary school.
Creativity	Methodology for explaining the topic	To achieve individualization of activities with a creative approach used in the educational process.
Communication using ICT.	Ability to transfer new knowledge using digital technologies.	Achieving technological stability through knowledge and practical activities in the electronic environment.

Figure 2. Contents of improving the components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers.

In our opinion, the components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers should be systematically developed and serve to improve existing capabilities.

It is appropriate to divide the components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers into 3 groups:

1. Stages of pedagogical development;
2. Selected methods of activity;
3. Contents of the implementation.

The content of improving the components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers is carried out in several contents and stages:

Implementation of the components of the mechanism for the development of independent labor and methodological competence through organic step-by-step processes aimed at independent learning:

- firstly, develop criteria for independent education;
- secondly, systematization of the content of self-study (textbook, website, web quest materials);
- determining the form of independent education;
- predicting the result of independent learning.

Implementation of the components of the mechanism for independent development of labor and methodological competence through master classes and the creation of a new environment.

- systematization of the content of theoretical knowledge;
- test acquired knowledge in practical activities;
- pay attention to the individualization of experience tested in practice;
- identify shortcomings of tested practical knowledge and transfer them as a practical lesson.

During these master classes, the future primary school teacher will pay attention to innovations in the science of primary education, the content of international assessment and the form of teaching. As a result, the components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers will take into account the technological progress of the stages of independent learning, master classes, as well as the dynamics of mastering innovations in subjects taught in primary school, and it will be possible to achieve individualization of their activities using a creative approach .

Considering the dynamics of assimilation of information on subjects taught in primary school, individualization of activity with a creative approach requires compliance with a number of mechanisms and components.

The main goal of the individualized approach is the education and development of a full-fledged teacher based on instrumental management technologies. At the present stage of innovative development of education, the task is to create conditions for the education of a comprehensive, competitive, independent teacher through the implementation of meaningful, systemic functions. The pedagogical significance of the individualized approach and the essence of teaching are reflected in the following: completely eliminate the mandatory discreteness of the educational process organized for the student, ensure its integrity; determine the possibility and ability to obtain independent knowledge and direction in the flow of developing information, provide flexibility in relation to this process; the inclusion of the student as a subject in the educational process is to ensure the complexity and harmonization of various effects in the activities of the teacher [12,17p]

Components of the mechanism for developing independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers, taking into account the dynamics of assimilation of innovations in the process of improvement through independent learning and master classes, individualization of activities with a creative approach, and also serves to improve methodological training. In our opinion, consideration of novelty and individualization of creative activity includes the following stages:

A step-by-step determination of the dynamics of independent learning for a future primary school teacher, technological development of the stages of master classes and assimilation of news on subjects taught in primary school:

trial classes are organized;

existing knowledge and competence are determined;

The content of e-learning materials is recommended taking into account the dynamics of development.

1. Determining the relevance of subjects taught in primary school, based on foreign experience, international assessment programs and technological development:

the content of the new generation textbook and targeted activities are integrated;

International experience content is included in every educational activity.

2. Pay special attention to the individualization of a creative approach to the activities of materials aimed at developing the independent labor and methodological competence of future primary school teachers:

it is possible to improve the list of sites aimed at improving methodological training in the direction of increasing independent labor and methodological competence;

materials presented in lectures must have creative content and be aimed at individualizing the activities of the future primary school teacher, aimed at improving his independent labor and methodological competence.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the creation and use of electronic educational resources by students is a consciously organized and controlled process, and a set of models developed based on the results of experimental studies contributes to the formation of the student's information culture.

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